

Enriching Students' Speech When Studying Russian Literature in Schools

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Abstract: This article examines specific problems related to the study of Russian literature in Uzbek schools. The author focuses on the main factors of interaction and mutual influence of language and literature, which operate in close interaction and are considered in individual modules only in order to more reliably reveal the individual aspects of the single process of mastering the treasures of Russian literature by schoolchildren. The enrichment of speech with phraseological units should correspond to the psychological and pedagogical characteristics of a certain age of students and meet certain criteria outlined in the article.

Keywords: factors of language interaction and mutual influence, lexicon semantics, phraseological units.

When considering specific problems related to the study of Russian literature, the factors of interaction and mutual influence of language and literature are taken into account in four aspects:

- 1) linguistic, which involves the comprehensive acquisition of language, as the linguistic material acts in its organized unity and in a broad context of its productive assimilation;
- 2) literary studies that ensure the fullness of literary education for students, their perception of cultural values as a source of spiritual enrichment in the broadest sense of the word;
- 3) general didactic, which allows to consider literary phenomena in their complex, to rely on already formed skills and abilities - literary and speech;
- 4) psychological-pedagogical, taking into account the specifics of students' perception of literature and defining the most rational ways of carrying out lexical-phraseological work to overcome the linguistic "barrier" [5, 124].

All these factors are closely interacting and are considered in individual modules only in order to more clearly reveal individual aspects of the unified process of students' mastery of Russian literature treasures.

Let's share our observations.

The first acquaintance with the text (small stories) can take place in the classroom with the use of the "read within yourself" technique. Such reading is aimed at performing certain methodological tasks. For example, to note in the text the place where it says why the protagonist of Mtsiri M. Yu. Lermontov ("Mtsiri") decided to flee to his homeland and why he died in a monastery. Or read A.P. Chekhov's story "Chameleon" "for yourself" and answer the questions: What happened in the market square? What do you mean by "chameleon"? Why does Ochumelov change his mind many times? What happened to the dog?

After first acquainting students with the text, the teacher begins to read the commentary. It is not necessary to think that the active role in the commentary reading belongs only to the teacher. Yes, the teacher himself reads the text aloud, but during the reading, he addresses the students with questions, gives small assignments that attract the students' attention to the meaning of the vocabulary material, the logical and poetic content of the text. Commentary reading aims not only to help students perceive the content of the text, but also to develop their listening culture. Therefore, the teacher should periodically change the reading rate of individual parts of the text, immediately checking the level of their assimilation by the students.

In the initial stage of learning, commentary is often based on students' native language. However, in the process of reading the text, the teacher should move as quickly as possible to commentary without translation, and all the vocabulary preparation should be carried out at the stage of the introductory lesson.

For example, when reading A.S. Pushkin's "Autumn" poem in the classroom, you can have a conversation about the signs of autumn in Uzbekistan, about the signs of late autumn in Russia, and during the reading of this poem, you can comment on the general points of the students' opinions. In the lesson, you should use RDM (distributive didactic material): a text describing late autumn in Russia and illustrations for it. Based on the content of the handout material, it is recommended to conduct a conversation during which new words from the text of A. Pushkin's poem are activated (these words should be reflected in the handout material - the description of late autumn in Russia). Then, answering the teacher's questions, the students compare the pictures of late autumn in Uzbekistan.

The vocabulary preparation of students for the perception of the text is most often carried out in the form of conversation. It is assumed that when conducting a conversation, a new vocabulary material for students cannot be introduced. That's not quite so. Our observations show that in the course of an introductory conversation, if its content consists of material from the students' life experience, one can introduce a few unknown words and expressions from the text being prepared for reading, and after explaining their meaning, one can continue the conversation by using the newly introduced words.

Enriching students' active vocabulary is a complex process. It is especially difficult to teach them to choose the right expressive word in context. Faced with the lexical richness of the Russian language and sometimes not finding proper support in their native language, schoolchildren find it difficult to choose the right word from the synonymous line and make mistakes.

The desire to "take arms" and introduce the most known words into one's speech often contradicts speech skills and abilities. For this purpose, you can recommend the following assignment: Describe the colonel from L. Tolstoy's story "After the Ball," paying attention to his attitude towards his daughter (politeness) and the Tatar prisoner (bad). (The word "politeness" in this context is just as inappropriate as the opposite word "bad.")

Students can also recommend tasks related to the study of phraseological units:

1. Explain the meaning of the following idioms. Think of a sentence using one of the following idioms:

- ☞ в двух шагах – очень близко-near;
- ☞ одного поля ягода – одинаковые-the same;
- ☞ водить за нос – обманывать-to lie;
- ☞ бить баклуши – бездельничать-idle;
- ☞ сломя голову – очень быстро-very soon;
- ☞ себе на уме – хитрый, скрытный-cunning;

2. Compile a short story using one (possibly two) of the proposed idioms, taking into account its meaning:

- со всех ног – очень быстро-very fast;
- без году неделя – недавно-recently;
- как свои пять пальцев – очень хорошо-very good;
- скрепя сердце – очень тяжело, болезненно-hardly, painfully;
- ни свет, ни заря – рано-early;
- в час по чайной ложке – медленно-slowly;
- стреляный воробей – опытный-experienced and so on.

Studying phraseological units significantly enhances students' knowledge of Russian vocabulary, and creates a foundation for the development of their speech. As a result of active work with phraseological units:

- enrichment of phraseological reserve;
- mastery of lexical and stylistic norms of the language;
- development of monologic speech;
- providing conditions for students to familiarize themselves with the linguistic features of literary works;
- the formation of a base for linguistic analysis of a literary text.

The enrichment of speech with phraseological units should correspond to the psychological and pedagogical characteristics of a certain age of students and meet the following criteria:

1. Phraseological units should be accessible to the students of the school, correspond to the level of development of students.
2. Phraseological units should conform to ethical norms, shape a worldview.
3. Phraseological units should be relevant in their ability to be used in various life situations.
4. Phraseological units should correspond to the grammatical material being studied.

The basic method of enriching the phraseological reserve of secondary school students is to cultivate a stable attention and interest in the phraseology of the native language, while the work should be built on the principle of "from simple to complex."

As a result of studying the phraseology, schoolchildren should acquire the following knowledge and skills:

- 1) to determine the lexical meaning of a phraseological unit, to distinguish it from the lexical meaning of individual words;
- 2) to find phraseological units in the text;
- 3) to give an interpretation of the lexical meaning of the phraseology taken from the context (descriptively or through the selection of synonyms);
- 4) to choose synonyms and antonyms for phraseological units;
- 5) to give examples of phraseological units;
- 6) to group phraseological units according to the given basis;
- 7) to define the function of using phraseological units in the text.

The modern requirements for learning motivate teachers to constantly seek new methods and techniques for work. In school dictionary work, four directions are combined: enriching the dictionary, that is, mastering new idioms that the schoolchildren did not know before; refining the dictionary: deepening the understanding of already known phraseological units, clarifying their shades, differences between them, choosing antonyms, analyzing polysemy, figurative meanings; activation of the dictionary: introducing as wide a range of phraseological units as possible into the speech of each student, introducing phraseological units into sentences, mastering the combination of phraseological units with other phraseological units, their appropriateness in use in a particular text, sometimes used by schoolchildren; correcting non-literary words, pronunciations, eliminating incorrect stresses.

In lessons, it is important to focus the attention of schoolchildren on the use of phraseological units in their own speech, thanks to which it becomes figurative and expressive. The work must be continuous, parallel to the work of the dictionary. It is very useful to create a dictionary in which students write down the phraseological combinations they have mastered. It is advisable to include in the dictionary the phraseological units whose components are the studied parts of speech. Such work contributes to the better assimilation and fixation of the passed parts of speech [4].

Therefore, the analysis of methodological literature on the study of vocabulary allows us to highlight the following methodological provisions:

- speech culture includes linguistic correctness, as well as speech correctness or skillful, skillful speech, where this understanding reflects the communicative aspect of speech culture, whose nature is closely related to the laws of the language as a whole;
- literature as one of the main subjects in teaching schoolchildren develops general reading skills and the ability to work with text, gives an idea of the richness of the Russian language, enriches speech through work on fiction, contributes to the general development of schoolchildren;
- work on phraseology should be carried out in conjunction with dictionary work;
- working on phraseological units will be productive if the following condition is met: phraseological units should be accessible to students and correspond to the phonetic, syntactic, stylistic features of the grammatical material studied in the school.

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